

Magnetic and ESR Studies on Mn(II) and Fe(III) Chelates of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol

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Manuscript received 9 August 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

Manganese(II) and Iron(III) complexes of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol (PAPL) have been prepared and characterized by magnetic susceptibility and ESR spectral measurements. Sextet ground state for manganese(II) complexes and doublet ground for iron(III) complexes have been inferred.

THE present communication describes preparation and characterization of Mn(II) and Fe(III) complexes of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol (PAPL). 2-Pyridylazo compounds have recently emerged out as an important class of chromogenic reagents¹, but very little work has been done on the structural aspects of their metal chelates²⁻⁵.

Experimental

(a) Preparation of ligands :

PAN was prepared by diazotization of 2-aminopyridine with butyl nitrite (freshly prepared from 1-butanol and sodium nitrite), followed by coupling of the isolated sodium diazotate with 2-naphthol in ethanol. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from ethanol.

PAPL² was prepared by the condensation of pyridylhydrazine with 2, 10 phenanthraquinone in acidic medium and precipitated by neutralization with aqueous ammonia (1 : 1). It was then recrystallised from dry benzene.

Preparation of complexes :

(i) *Manganese(II)-complexes*—15 ml of 0.1M aqueous solution of $MnCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was added to an ethanolic solution of the ligands (750 mg of PAN or 900 mg of PAPL in 500 ml ethanol). pH of the solution was raised to 10.0 by adding sodium hydroxide solution. The contents were refluxed on a water-bath for about two hours, when intense pink colour developed. On concentration the complexes separated out as crystalline granules. The same were filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol and acetone and dried in an electric oven at 60°.

(ii) *Iron(III)-complexes*—15.0 ml 0.1M $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ solution was added to the ethanolic solution of ligands (750/900 mg of PAN/PAPL) and the contents were refluxed for two hours. On concentration, the complex separated out as brown powder. These were worked out as in the case of manganese(II) complex. Results of elemental analysis are presented in Table 1.

All the complexes are insoluble in water and

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA

Complex	pH of isolation	Colour	m.p. °C	% M Calcd. (found)	% C Calcd. (found)	% N Calcd. (found)	% H Calcd. (found)
$Mn(C_{15}H_{10}N_2O)$	10.0	Pink	300	9.89 (9.99)	65.20 (65.24)	15.14 (15.24)	3.59 (3.63)
$Mn(C_{19}H_{12}N_2O)$	10.0	Pink	300	7.90 (8.00)	65.21 (66.42)	12.01 (12.24)	3.98 (4.07)
$Fe(C_{15}H_{10}N_2O)_2ClO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	3.0	Brown	300	8.12 (8.12)	52.04 (52.37)	12.32 (12.40)	3.40 (3.49)
$Fe(C_{15}H_{12}N_2O)_2ClO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	3.0	Brown	300	6.92 (7.09)	57.46 (57.92)	10.68 (10.66)	3.55 (3.55)

dissolve in the common organic solvents viz., chloroform, pyridine, dimethylformamide and nitrobenzene.

Physical measurements :

The ESR spectra of the complexes as powdered samples or as pyridine solution were recorded on an X-Band Varian V-4502-12 EPR spectrometer. The low-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy Balance using mercuric tetrathiocyanate cobaltate(II) as calibrant.

Results and Discussion

Manganese(II) complexes :

Mn(II)-PAN and Mn(II)-PAPL complexes show magnetic moments of 6.31 B. M. and 6.48 B. M. respectively (Table 2) indicating sextet ground state⁶⁻⁸. The higher magnetic moment values may be attributed to cooperative phenomena.

These observations indicate larger asymmetry in Mn(II)-PAPL complex than in Mn(II)-PAN complex. May be that PAN in its complex with manganese(II) coordinates through all the three coordination centres viz., the heterocyclic nitrogen, the nitrogen of the azo group farthest from pyridine ring and the hydroxyl group, while PAPL acts as a bidentate ligand, coordinating through the oxygen of the hydroxyl group and the nitrogen of the azo group nearer to the phenanthrene ring, the axial positions being occupied by the water molecule. In pyridine solution, the solvent molecules replace the water molecules from the axial positions and the resulting ligand field assumes almost the same symmetry as obtained from two terdentate PAN molecules. The EPR parameters have been calculated and are summarised in Table 3. Zero field splitting parameter for the Mn(II)-PAPL complex (in solid state) comes out to be 0.082 cm⁻¹.

Iron(III) complexes :

Results of magnetic susceptibility measurements

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Complex	Temp. °K	X _g × 10 ⁶ (c.g.s.)	χ _M × 10 ⁶ (c.g.s.)	χ _M × 10 ² (c.g.s.)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
Mn(PAN) ₂	295.0	28.17	16540.0	16867.0	6.31
Mn(PAPL) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	294.0	25.17	17420.0	17121.0	6.48
Fe(PAN) ₂ ·ClO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	293.0	2.004	1378.0	1737.0	2.023
Fe(PAL) ₂ ·ClO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	295.0	1.738	1372.0	1805.0	2.06
	206.0	2.794	2200.0	2633.0	2.08
	174.8	3.166	2494.0	2827.0	1.99
	153.7	3.714	2924.0	3357.0	2.03
	121.5	4.599	3622.0	4055.0	1.98
	110.0	5.148	4054.0	4487.0	1.99
	87.5	5.478	4313.0	4746.0	1.92

The EPR Spectrum of Mn(II)-PAN complex (solid) shows one almost symmetric signal centred around g=2.00. A similar but narrower signal is obtained from pyridine solution. Mn(II)-PAPL complex on the other hand gives in solid state a spectrum indicative of the presence of zero field splitting and hence of ligand field component of very low symmetry. Further, in the spectrum of the pyridine solution, of the complex, the zero field splitting phenomenon is not observed.

on the complexes are given in Table 2. χ_M' vs. T curve for Fe(III)-PAPL is shown in Fig. 1. Curie Weiss law for the complex is obeyed (θ = -18°K) and temperature independent moment of 2.00 B.M. is observed. A doublet ground state is indicated. For low-spin octahedral complexes with ground term ³T_{2g}, the magnetic moment values higher than spin-only values upto 2.5 B. M. are expected. The magnetic moment could be temperature dependent because of the spin orbit coupling interaction and

TABLE 3—EPR PARAMETERS

Complex	Medium	g	Zero field splitting (gauss) (cm ⁻¹)	
Mn (PAN) ₂	Powder	2.00	—	—
Mn (PAN) ₂	Pyridine	2.00	—	—
Mn (PAPL) ₂	Powder	2.00	819.8	0.82
Mn (PAPL) ₂	Pyridine	2.02	—	—
Complex	Medium	g	g	
Fe (PAN) ₂ ·ClO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Powder	2.22	1.96	
Fe (PAL) ₂ ·ClO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Powder	2.22	1.93	

the extent of this temperature dependence will be

Fig. 1. Temperature Dependence of χ_M for Fe(III)-PAPL complex.

decided largely by the splitting of the ${}^2T_{2g}$ in a ligand field of low symmetry. Figgis *et al.*^{9,10} have pointed towards limitations inherent in the above statement. The marked temperature independence of magnetic moment in Fe(III)-PAPL indicates the splitting of the triply degenerate ${}^2T_{2g}$ ground term under the influence of obvious low symmetry of the ligand field. This view gets support from the ESR data discussed below.

From the ESR spectra of the complexes, the 'g' values have been calculated following Kheubuhl¹¹ and presented in Table 3. EPR spectra of the low-spin iron (III) complexes with octahedral crystal fields of high symmetries, where the ground term is essentially ${}^2T_{2g}$, show two characteristic properties. The ESR signals are observed only at the very low temperature and the 'g' values vary greatly from 2.0023. This is because three orbital states of t_{2g} , close in energy, are connected by the spin orbital operator. The complexes under discussion on the other hand show ESR signals at room temperature

and also the 'g' factors are not far from 2.0023. This suggests that the ground state is not essentially ${}^2T_{2g}$ and that some of its orbital degeneracy has been removed by the low symmetry component of the ligand field.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. Mitra, Chemical Physics Group, Tata Institute For Fundamental Research, Bombay, to Prof. T. R. Govindachary, Director, CIBA-GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay and to Dr. B. S. Joshi, Scientist, Radiochemistry Division, BARC, Bombay for providing facilities for low-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements, microanalysis and ESR measurements, respectively. The work was carried out under the Financial Assistance to Teachers' scheme awarded to one of the authors by the University Grants Commission, New Delhi.

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